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IMPLEMENTATION OF ENHANCED SCHOOL IMPROVEMENT PLAN (ESIP) CORRELATES TO SCHOOL PERFORMANCE IN MORONG: BASIS FOR INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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ABSTRACT

The present study aimed to assess the level of implementation of an enhanced school improvement plan and its correlation with school performance in Rizal, particularly in Cluster 1 in Morong District, during the school year 2023-2024.

The respondents of the study were the teachers of all elementary schools in the said cluster, including Caniogan Elementary School, Maybancal Elementary School, Roman Tantiongoc Elementary School, Talaga Elementary School, TCM Elementary School, San Guillermo Elementary School, Bombongan Elementary School employing a total respondent of 180 teachers. The study utilized a descriptive research method, employing survey questionnaires as the primary data-gathering instrument. The analysis and interpretation of findings was based on the responses gathered from the survey questionnaire designed by the researcher to gauge teachers' perceptions and experiences regarding implementing the school improvement plan. The study was conducted from January-May 2024.

However, the scope of the study is delimited by its geographical location, as it is limited to schools within Cluster 1 of Morong District in Rizal, excluding other districts in the division. Secondly, the timeframe is confined to the school year 2023-2024, restricting data collection, analysis, and interpretation within this period. Thirdly, the respondents are solely limited to teachers within the selected schools, omitting other stakeholders such as students, parents, or administrators from the survey.

The findings revealed that most of the respondents were of the age 21-25 years' old. Majority of the respondents were female and college graduates. Most of the teachers have experience of 6-10 years. In terms of ACCESS, the overall weighted mean obtained was 3.70 which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree". In terms of EQUITY the overall weighted mean obtained was 3.29 which is interpreted as "Agree". In terms of Quality, the overall weighted mean obtained was 3.57 which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree". In terms of governance, the overall weighted mean obtained was 3.66 which is interpreted as "Strongly Agree". There is no significant difference in the level implementation of enhanced school improvement plan when grouped according to profile. The

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performance of school in School Based Management during the last school year 2022-2023 were maturing stage or SBM level 2. There is no significant relationship between the level implementation of enhanced school improvement plan and school performance.

Based on the findings of the study therefore, the researcher concluded the level implementation of enhanced school improvement plan and profile of the respondents showed no significant difference. The level implementation of enhanced school improvement plan and the school performance in SBM showed no significant relationship.

Key Words: *Enhanced School Improvement PLAN (ESIP), School Performance, School-Based Management (SBM)*

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